

A distributed network of heritage information - February 2018

by Enno Meijers (enno.meijers@kb.nl), Sjors de Valk (sjors@sjorsdevalk.nl), Wilbert Helmus (wilbert.helmus@netwerkdigitaalergoed.nl)

INTRODUCTION

The Dutch Digital Heritage Network ('NDE') is a partnership that focuses on developing a sector wide digital infrastructure of national facilities and services for improving the visibility, usability and sustainability of digital heritage. The Network was established in 2015 on the initiative of the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science. Key partners within NDE are national heritage institutions, the National Library, the National Archives, The Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision, the Netherlands Cultural Heritage Agency and the Humanities Cluster of the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences, and a growing number of partners both within and outside the heritage sector. NDE is responsible for realizing a joint strategy program for the Dutch cultural heritage network. The goal is a distributed network build by the institutes and their stakeholders, each contributing from their own perspective and in their own capacity. The program consists of a three layered approach focussed on the management of data collections ('sustainability'), the infrastructure for connecting the data ('usability') and applications for presenting and using the data ('visibility').

DISCOVERY INFRASTRUCTURE

This article describes the long term vision NDE is developing for a discovery infrastructure for the Dutch heritage collections and the work that is being doing in this respect at the 'usability' layer. We expect to improve the usability of the collection data maintained by the heritage institutions by implementing Linked Data principles in all levels of the network. The NDE program supports heritage institutions to align their collection data with shared Linked Data resources, such as thesauri, and to publish their data as Linked Open Data. Our goal is to develop a lightweight cross-domain discovery infrastructure that is build on a distributed architecture.

One of the core functionalities in the usability layer is a 'network of terms' that supports discovery of shared definitions for places, people, concepts, time periods. These terms are made accessible through a search API that provides URIs pointing to the terms in the distributed sources. Collection management systems can address this API to search for relevant terms when cultural heritage objects are being annotated. As a result references to formalized terms (URIs) will be added to the object descriptions. IT suppliers are encouraged to support the publishing of collection metadata as Linked Data. A reference architecture for the Dutch digital heritage network (DERA) that will formalize the publication of Linked Data is under development. The NDE program makes all relevant terminology sources, maintained by the institutions, available as Linked Data and provides facilities for term alignment and building new terminologie sources. Tools like CultuurLINK [1], PoolParty [2], OpenSKOS [3] are being provided by the NDE network.

BROWSABLE LINKED DATA

Having cultural heritage institutions publish their data as Linked Open Data with references to shared definitions for places, people, concepts and time periods is one part of the challenge. The other is to provide means for navigating in a cross-domain, user-centric fashion. Based on possible relevant URIs identified in the user queries we want to be able to identify the relevant and available Linked Data in the cultural heritage network. In general the concept of 'browsable linked data' is still a

challenging concept. Although Tim Berners-Lee describes the concept of ‘browsable graphs’ and even states that statements which relate things in two documents must be repeated in each, this is not a common practice in the Linked Data world [4]. The current practice is to offer Linked Data in a ‘follow your nose’ fashion which is only based on using *forward links* to point to other resources.

In order to navigate in a bidirectional way through the Linked Open Data cloud, support for navigation based on *backlinks* is needed. Most Linked Data projects support bidirectional browsing by physical aggregation of Linked Data sources. Using this aggregated data in triplestore databases both entries to the resource can be queried. This approach requires data replication and large central infrastructures and does not comply with our vision for a distributed network of digital heritage information.

An alternative approach is virtual data integration using federated queries. Unfortunately the current Linked Data solutions (triplestores with SPARQL endpoints) are hard to implement for small organizations and often suffer from performance issues in a federated setting. A promising approach is the implementation of the Linked Data Fragments framework [5], which we are currently investigating. But even using federated querying based on Linked Data Fragments leaves the question which endpoints have relevant data for a specific user question. Random querying all the possible endpoints in our network using Linked Data Fragments would be impractical and unrealistic. A preselection of data sources relevant for the query is necessary.

REGISTRY

These considerations have led to our decision to build a (preferably distributed and automated) registry that records backlinks for all the terms used in the digital heritage network. The registry contains the formal Linked Data definitions of the institutions and datasets in our network. Based on this information a Knowledge Graph is constructed as a ‘network of relations’ describing the relations between the data sources and the shared terms in our network. These relations facilitate navigating from URIs related to the user query back to the object descriptions in the collections.

We have described the intended functionality for our distributed network of heritage information in a high-level design [6], which will be updated in May 2018. We are maturing the design and implementing parts of the functionality together with a range of heritage and research institutions.

- [1]: <http://cultuurlink.beeldengeluid.nl>
- [2]: <https://www.poolparty.biz/>
- [3]: <https://github.com/OpenSKOS>
- [4]: <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>
- [5]: [Towards sustainable publishing and querying of distributed Linked Data archives](#)
- [6]: <https://github.com/netwerk-digitaal-erfgoed/high-level-design>